

Application and Modification of Phosphate-Bearing Rock in Myanmar as a Potential Mineral Fertilizer

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Abstract

Phosphate rock is the basic material used in all phosphorus fertilizer production. In Myanmar, phosphate rocks are found in Shan State, Mon State, Kayah State and Mandalay Division. In this work, phosphate minerals as phosphorite samples were collected from Thabeikyin area in Mandalay Division. The phosphorite mineral consists of 8.59 % of P_2O_5 which is modified by wet screening and hydroseparation method to upgrade the phosphate content. Phosphate fertilizers; phosphoric acid, normal and triple superphosphate were prepared from upgraded phosphate powder (14.56 % P_2O_5) by using concentrated sulphuric acid, H_2SO_4 . Analyses of the prepared phosphate fertilizers were carried out by using conventional and modern instrumental techniques. The prepared phosphoric acid was found to contain 8.74% of P_2O_5 , and the content of primary and secondary nutrients of superphosphates were 15.42% of P_2O_5 , 8.65% of Ca, 11.78 % of S and 7.3 % of K_2O in normal superphosphate and 18.94 % P_2O_5 , 8.32 % of Ca and 3.5 % of S in triple superphosphate. The prepared fertilizers were used as mineral inorganic fertilizers in the growth and yield of two selected crops; maize and eggplant on neutral clay soil. Field studies show that the prepared phosphate fertilizers were able to produce a higher percentage yield of vegetables 1981.94 kg/ha for maize and 32291 kg/ha for eggplant than to the control soil. Comparative study of all fertilizers treatment was made and found that after the harvesting stage, triple superphosphate fertilizer treated soil has higher nutrients contents compared to the original control soil. From the field work investigations, it was observed that prepared phosphate fertilizers promote plant growth, aggregate soil particles, improve physical conditions of soil and also enhance the yield of the crops.

Key words: phosphate rock, phosphate fertilizer, normal superphosphate, phosphoric acid, triple superphosphate, maize, eggplant

Introduction

The element phosphorus is known to be present in more than 150 minerals, most of which belong to the apatite family of calcium phosphates. Phosphorus, an essential constituent for all living organisms, is one of the least abundant of the mineral nutrients. The availability of large quantities of phosphate rock is of primary importance to agricultural and industrial nations (Smith, 1961). Phosphate rock is the starting point for all phosphorus fertilizer. The principal phosphate mineral from the most deposits is francolite, a carbonate fluorapatite represented by the formula $Ca_{10}F_2(PO_4)_6 \cdot X CaCO_3$ (Website-1). Phosphate fertilizer production primarily involves the mining and conversion of phosphate rock to more soluble phosphorus compounds which can be effectively utilized by plant. Phosphate rock is the only economical source of phosphorus for manufacturing phosphate fertilizers and chemicals. Phosphate rock may be ground very finely and applied directly to the soil, or it may be used in the manufacture of superphosphate. Certain chemical process, such as, the solubilization of phosphate rock with acid have been basic to the phosphate industry to many years. However, continued technological improvements have resulted in more economical production of higher analysis better quality products by this process. A large number of phosphorus compounds are either used for the direct fertilization of crops or are found as constituents of mixed fertilizers. A tremendous amount of research has been conducted to evaluate these compounds as sources of P for plants growth on a wide variety of soils (Kilmer & Webb, 1968).

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Materials and Methods

The chemicals used in this research work purchased from “British Drug House (BDH) Chemical Ltd., Poole, England”, “Kanto Chemical Co., Ltd., Japan”, and “Hopkin and Williams, Co., Ltd, England”, “Merck Darmstadt, Germany” and “Sigma-Aldrich Co., Germany and England”

Sampling

Representative phosphate rock sample were received from 5 mile station in Thabeikyin Township, Mandalay Division. Raw phosphate rock sample was ground and sieved and then kept in an air tight plastic bag. The conventional and modern instrumental techniques were used in analysis of phosphate rock sample.

Preparation of Upgraded Phosphate Powder

Raw phosphate rock samples were firstly ground and passed through 4-mesh sieve. The phosphate rock was mixed with deionized water in the weight ratio 1:2 and stirred thoroughly. Coagulated solution was decanted and filtered by using filter paper (Whatman No.1). The obtained upgraded phosphate powder was washed with distilled water and dried. It was expressed in percentage and amount of P_2O_5 was determined spectrometrically at 460 nm. The conventional and modern instrumental techniques(ED-XRF, XRD, AAS, UV-Visible) were used in analysis of phosphate rock and upgraded phosphate sample.

Preparation of Normal Superphosphate Fertilizer from Upgraded phosphate sample

Upgraded phosphate samples of sufficient fineness to pass a 4-mesh sieve and calculated amount of sulphuric acid were needed to prepare phosphate fertilizer. Upgraded phosphate powder was mixed with water in the weight ratio of 1:1. The sulphuric acid was added one and half time of the volume of water. This mixture was stirred for half-an hour. After stirring, the slurry was formed (Collings, 1955). The slurry was allowed to solidify for two days. After that the resulting porous solid was disintegrated to mature or cure during a period of 2 weeks. To obtain granular phosphate the solid was crushed, sieved, air-dried and stored in a plastic bag.

Preparation of Phosphoric Acid from Upgraded phosphate sample

Phosphoric acid was prepared by higher ratio (25 ml) of sulphuric acid is different percent (5%, 6%, 7%, 8%, 9%, 10%, 20%, 30%, 40%, 50%) to (1g) of upgraded phosphate powder. The resulting solution of phosphoric acid and solid calcium sulphate were mixed in suspension. The calcium sulphate was separated by filtration, giving a large quantity of waste by-product.

Preparation of Triple Superphosphate Fertilizer from Upgraded phosphate sample

When upgraded phosphate powder was treated with prepared phosphoric acid in the weight ratio (1:1), triple superphosphate (TSP) was obtained. The operation was quite similar to that for making normal superphosphate but the product has more than twice the P_2O_5 content because phosphoric acid was used rather than sulphuric acid. It was produced as granular and non-granular forms. Analysis of prepared phosphate fertilizers were carried out by using conventional and modern instrumental techniques (EDXRF, XRD, AAS, UV-Visible).

Field Experiment

Assay of Soil Used for Cultivation of Plants

The soil is the farm near Maubin University was collect and subjected to physical and chemical analysis using conventional and modern techniques. Some part of this research work

was done in the Soil Analysis Laboratory, Department of Land Use and Seed Division, Myanmar Agriculture Service under Ministry of Agriculture and Irrigation. The soil sample taking before plantation and after harvesting, were analysed.

Collection of Soil Sample

Soil samples were taken from 5-10 cm depth of each treated plot. Sufficient quantities of soil were taken from five points within each plot in order to achieve more representative samples. No special effort was made to protect the soil from contaminations. The field trial at the farm near Maubin University was conducted to study the effect of prepared phosphoric acid, normal and triple superphosphate fertilizer on the plant growth and quality of cultivated plants. The comparison study on the performance of prepared phosphate fertilizers in the cultivation of maize and eggplant on neutral clay soil was done.

Results and Discussion

Upgrading of Local Phosphate Rock

Phosphorus raw materials possess unrelated impurities in the form of acid soluble minerals which contain Fe, Al, Mg, etc. The main types of phosphate rocks are apatite and phosphorite. In Myanmar, phosphate minerals as phosphorite occurred at the Thabeikyin area in Mandalay Division is the most prominent. The collected phosphate mineral sample from Thabeikyin Township consists of 8.59% of P_2O_5 , which is low content of phosphate and may not be used directly as fertilizers. Thus it is necessary to modify collected phosphate rock samples, so as to remove impurities and to upgrade the phosphate content, which is modified by wet screening and hydroseseparation methods were employed.

Figure 1. Local phosphate rock sample (phosphorite mineral)

Figure 2. XRD diffractogram of local phosphate rock

Characterization of Phosphate Rock & Upgraded Phosphate Sample

Table 1 indicated that the pH value of samples, i.e., pH 5.1 for phosphate rock and pH 6.0 for upgraded phosphate sample were suitable to prepare phosphate fertilizers. The solubility data indicated that the upgraded sample was more soluble than that of phosphate rock sample. The amount of phosphorus content % and content of elements such as potassium, calcium, magnesium, iron and zinc were shown in Table 1. The most important parameter characterizing the quality of the upgraded phosphate sample is P_2O_5 content (14.56%) is higher than phosphate rock (8.59%).

Phosphate rock sample was identified by using X-ray diffraction method. The diffractogram of phosphate rock was shown in figure 2. Based on computer matched patterns, Thabeikyin phosphate rock sample consisted of two types of phosphate minerals; Vantasselle $Al_4(PO_4)_3 \cdot 9H_2O$ and Brushite $CaHPO_4(2H_2O)_2$.

The presence of major elements phosphorus, calcium, iron, potassium, chlorine and titanium in raw phosphate rock and upgraded phosphate materials are shown by ED-XRF spectra represented in Figure 3 and 4, respectively. The data depicted in figures confirmed the higher amount of phosphorus content in upgraded sample.

Figure 3. ED-XRF spectrum of local phosphate rock sample

Figure 4. ED-XRF spectrum of upgraded phosphate sample

Table 1. Physicochemical analysis data of Thabeikyin Phosphate Rock and upgraded Phosphate Powder

No.	Item	Phosphate Rock	Upgraded Phosphate Powder
1	pH	5.10	6.00
2	Moisture (%)	2.75	1.38
3	Solubility (%)	17.81	36.47
4	P ₂ O ₅ (%)	8.59	14.56
5	Ca (ppm)	104.50	118.20
6	Mg (ppm)	5.64	4.31
7	Fe (ppm)	98.81	76.12
8	K (ppm)	5189	53.72
9	Zn (ppm)	10.90	7.43

Preparation and Characterization of Phosphate Fertilizers

(a) prepared phosphoric acid (b) prepared normal superphosphate (c) prepared triple superphosphate

Figure 5. Prepared phosphate fertilizers

Phosphoric acid (H₃PO₄) is an important intermediate in the production of phosphate fertilizers. It is an intermediate for mixed fertilizers, both liquid and solid. In this work, wet process H₃PO₄ was produced by using a higher ratio of H₂SO₄ on ground upgraded phosphate sample. Wet-process phosphoric acid is an impure product containing a complex system of impurities that include compound of Fe, Ca and K, as well as free H₂SO₄ and organic matter. A portion of the impurities is present as solid due to imperfect filtration and precipitation during and after concentration. Percentage of P₂O₅ content in prepared phosphoric acid with respect to

their ratio of 1g of upgraded phosphate sample with 25ml of different concentration (%) of sulphuric acid are presented in Table 2. Using 9% sulphuric acid gave the highest amount of P₂O₅ content 8.74% in aprepared phosphoric acid. The separation of the acid from the sulphate was carried out several times so as to obtain the concentrated phosphoric acid.

Figure 6. XRD diffractogram of prepared normal superphosphate fertilizer

Figure 7. XRD diffractogram of prepared triple superphosphate fertilizer

Table 2. Percentage of P₂O₅ Content in Prepared Phosphoric Acid with respect to their Ratio of 1 g of Upgraded Phosphate Sample with 25mL of Different Concentrations of Sulphuric acid

Sample No.	H ₂ SO ₄ Concn. (%)	P ₂ O ₅ (%)
1	5	6.97
2	6	7.25
3	7	7.59
4	8	8.05
5	9	8.74
6	10	8.28
7	20	7.78
8	30	7.58
9	40	7.36
10	50	7.26

Figure 8. ED-XRF spectrum of prepared phosphoric acid

Table 3. Physicochemical Analysis Data of the Prepared Normal Superphosphate Fertilizer

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Normal
 Superphosphate
 Normal
 Superphosphate
 4.4
 5.
 36
 5.36
 39
 .35
 15
 .42
 7.
 3 8
 .65
 11
 .78

39.3
 5 1
 5.42
 7.
 3 8
 .65
 11
 .78

15.4
 2 7
 .3
 7.3
 8.
 65
 8.65
 11
 .78

11.7
 8

Table 4. Physicochemical Analysis Data of the Prepared triple Superphosphate Fertilizer

Sample	pH	Moisture	pH	Moisture	Moisture	(%) Solubility	Solubility	(%) P ₂ O ₅	P ₂ O ₅	(%) Ca	Ca	(%) S	S
(%) Triple Superphosphate	4.5	4.35	47.52	18.94	8.32	2.5							
Triple Superphosphate	4.5	4.35	47.52	18.94	8.32	2.5							
Triple Superphosphate	4.5	4.35	47.52	18.94	8.32	2.5							
	4.5	4.35	47.52	18.94	8.32	2.5							
	4.35	47.52	18.94	8.32	2.5								
	47.52	18.94	8.32	2.5									
	18.94	8.32	2.5										
	8.32	2.5											
	2.5												

The phosphate rock $\text{Ca}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2$, is not very useful because of its exceedingly low solubility. When treated with sulphuric acid, however phosphate rock becomes more soluble; and the resulting mixture of phosphate and phosphate salt of calcium is called superphosphate. Normal superphosphate is made by treating ground phosphate rock with sulphuric acid in approximately equal proportions by weight. The acid-treating process, called acidulation, of the phosphate rock converts the relatively insoluble tricalcium phosphate in the rock to the monocalcium form-an available form. In this work, normal superphosphate was prepared by using different percent of sulphuric acid to upgraded phosphate powder sample. Physicochemical analysis data of the normal superphosphate fertilizer is reported in Table 3. The solubility of prepared normal superphosphate fertilizers significantly soluble compared to upgraded phosphate sample. Since its P_2O_5 content is 15.42%, which is in the range of superphosphate this prepared fertilizer can be termed as normal superphosphate.

Triple superphosphate fertilizer can be prepared with low cost of production equipments for the best quality. Regional small scale plants for phosphate fertilizer production can be easily provided in Myanmar depending on enough supply of raw materials. In this work, triple superphosphate (TSP) fertilizer, which was prepared by using prepared phosphoric acid and upgraded phosphate powder sample. Physicochemical analysis data of the prepared normal and triple superphosphate fertilizers are presented in Table 3 and 4. The solubility of prepared triple superphosphate fertilizer is significantly higher than that of prepared normal superphosphate fertilizer. Although the calcium content of triple superphosphate was about the same as that of normal superphosphate, the triple superphosphate has higher P_2O_5 content and lower S content. It means to say that the prepared triple superphosphate fertilizer contains very little calcium sulphate which is in accordance with the specified commercial triple superphosphate fertilizer.

Figure 6 and 7 are the XRD diffractograms of prepared normal and triple superphosphate fertilizers respectively. These diffractograms clearly indicated specific sharp peaks at respective 2θ values. The resulting data, for instance, calcium, phosphorus and sulphur compound can be justified by the XRD peaks presented in figures, which is in accordance with the search-match computed display. The prepared normal superphosphate fertilizer was matched with large amount of calcium sulphate and Brushite $\text{CaPO}_3(\text{OH}) \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ as well as calcium hydrogen phosphate $\text{CaH}_2(\text{PO}_4)_2$. The diffractogram of prepared triple superphosphate fertilizer indicated the presence of calcium hydrogen phosphate and its hydrate. On this context, the prepared superphosphate fertilizers are different in nature so that they can be termed as normal and triple superphosphate based on the CaSO_4 content.

Field Experiment

The field experiments were conducted at the farm (near Maubin University, Maubin Township, Ayeyarwaddy Division). The total of four experimental plots for each plant, were established. Factors affecting plant growth are air, heat (temperature), light, mechanical support, nutrients and water. In the field experiment, these external factors except nutrients supplying to soil were same condition for all treated soils and control plot. Fertilizers are used to increase the supply of available plant nutrients in the soil and also to balance the plant nutrients ratio. The effect of phosphate fertilizers on the plant growth was studied in this work. During cultivation, monthly determination of plant height, the most important agronomic characters of the cultivation, was carried out. Prepared triple superphosphate treated plot (T_1) is the maximum. Data obtained from these determinations are presented in Table 8. After harvesting, maize grain of the yield components such as number of ear per plot, number of kernels per ear, and weight of thousand grains were measured and yield was estimated. Weight depends on genetic, environmental and cultural practices. Means for these characteristics are shown in Table 6. The maximum grain yield of about 1981.94 kg/ha was obtained by using prepared triple superphosphate treated plot (T_1). Eggplant of the yield components such as weight of fruit per plant and weight per fruit were measure and yield were estimated. Moreover, length per fruit and fresh weight of whole plant were also measured. The data are present in Table 7. The maximum fruit yield of about 32291 kg/ha was obtained using prepared triple superphosphate treated plot (T_1).

Plant analysis is a suitable tool for determining the nutrients uptake of the plants. So, the phosphorus distribution in vegetative parts (leaves, stems and roots) of the plant was determined after harvesting. The results mentioned in Table 10, show that vegetative parts of plant such as stem and roots vary to a higher extent in their mineral composite than leaves. The data represented the results of the different phosphate fertilizers treatment effect on the maturity stage of the plant. It can be interpreted that all different of phosphate fertilizers, the highest phosphorus uptake was found in plant with triple superphosphate treated plot (T_1). It can be reported that increased in vegetative growth as well as early maturity can be achieved using prepared triple superphosphate treated plot (T_1).

The largest chemical component of the kernel is protein. Not only maize grains can be considered as a source of energy but also they can provide significant amount of protein. Protein and fats as well as dietary fibre can be found in greatest amounts (FAO, 1992). From the data as shown in Table 8, the highest protein, ash, phosphorus, calcium and potassium contents were observed in grain taken from prepared triple superphosphate treated plot (T_1). So it can be said that the quality, in term of nutritive values, was significantly improved by using prepared phosphate fertilizers.

Table 5. Analysis Data of the Farm Soil before Transplanting

No	Item	T ₁	T ₂	T ₃	T ₄
1	Texture – Sand (%)	17.23	17.20	17.21	17.15
	Silt (%)	34.16	34.12	34.11	34.05
	Clay (%)	44.91	44.92	44.90	44.85
	Total (%)	96.30	96.24	96.22	96.05
2	Moisture (%)	6.73	6.69	6.71	6.68
3	pH	6.1	6.3	5.9	6.5
4	Electrical Conductivity (mS/ cm)	0.175	0.173	0.197	0.116
5	Organic Carbon (%)	0.79	0.75	0.78	0.74
6	Humus (%)	4.49	4.35	3.17	3.48
7	Total N (%)	0.148	0.149	0.144	0.135
8	Available P (ppm)	42.59	31.53	37.97	20.36
9	Available K ₂ O (mg/ 100 g)	14.46	13.64	12.32	11.72
10	Exchangeable Ca ⁺⁺ (mmol/ 100 g)	13.57	13.34	11.92	11.406
11	Exchangeable Mg ⁺⁺ (mmol/ 100 g)	0.637	0.635	0.523	0.513

T₁ = triple superphosphate treated soil
T₂ = normal superphosphate treated soil
T₃ = phosphoric acid treated soil
T₄ = control

Figure 9. The growth of maize and eggplant cultivated before harvesting

Table 6. Physical Properties of Cultivated Maize and Eggplant after Harvesting Stage

Treatment	Ear Length (cm)	Diameter of Ear (cm)	Kernel/ Ear	Kernel Row/ Ear	Length of Kernel Row (cm)	Kernel/ Row	Weight of Thousand Grains (g)	Grain Yield (kg/ha)
T ₁	15.12	8.38	340.7	14	14.52	27.83	206.64	1981.94

T ₂	13.89	8.21	297.56	14	14.32	25.63	197.7	1656.73
T ₃	14.23	8.28	310.54	14	14.39	26.54	198.51	1735.81
T ₄	11.76	7.28	135.82	12	13.8	19.17	189.58	725.47

Table 7. Physical Properties of Cultivated Eggplant after Harvesting Stage

Treatment	Life time (day)	Plant height at 120 DAE (cm)	Fresh-weight of whole plant (g)	Weight of fruit per plant (g)	Weight per fruit (g)	Length per fruit (cm)	Yield kg/ ha
T ₁	120	99.9	930	1530	230	26.3	32291
T ₂	120	95.21	920	1347	215	25.5	28414
T ₃	120	98.35	925	1459	227	25.9	30784
T ₄	120	82.71	520	919	75	19.5	19373

Table 8. Effect of Prepared Phosphate Fertilizers on Maize and Eggplant Height

Treatment	Plant mean height of maize (cm)			Plant mean height of eggplant (cm)			
	30 d	60 d	90 d	30 d	60 d	90 d	120 d
T ₁	27.69	95.36	191.76	8.7	37.94	91.73	99.9
T ₂	24.95	91.72	189.53	8.3	35.82	84.44	95.21
T ₃	25.35	93.93	190.85	7.5	36.37	90.71	98.35
T ₄	20.91	83.51	151.36	7.3	35.61	79.52	82.71

Table 9. Nutritional Analysis Data of Maize Grain and Eggplant Fruit obtained from Different Treated Plots

Constituent (%)	Maize grain				Eggplant fruit			
	T ₁	T ₂	T ₃	T ₄	T ₁	T ₂	T ₃	T ₄
Moisture	9.53	9.47	9.57	9.5	92.7	93.1	92.2	92.5
Protein	12.41	12.06	12.36	11.9	1.08	0.97	1.05	0.85
Potassium	0.327	0.304	0.319	0.297	0.0024	0.0019	0.0021	0.0012
Ash	1.42	1.43	1.41	1.4	0.24	0.25	0.23	0.22
Phosphorus	0.501	0.385	0.49	0.321	0.047	0.039	0.042	0.031
Calcium	0.048	0.039	0.042	0.031	0.019	0.014	0.018	0.0012

Table 10. Phosphorus Uptake by Vegetative Parts of Maize Plant and Eggplant after Harvesting

Treatment	Phosphorus content of maize plant (%)			Phosphorus content of eggplant (%)		
	Leaf	Stem	Root	Leaf	Stem	Root
T ₁	0.17	0.29	0.45	0.19	0.31	0.44
T ₂	0.12	0.22	0.41	0.16	0.28	0.39
T ₃	0.15	0.26	0.43	0.17	0.29	0.42
T ₄	0.09	0.2	0.39	0.16	0.25	0.35

In the present work, the moisture content of eggplant was determined by oven-drying method. The moisture contents of eggplant, was found to be in the range of 92.2-93.1 %. The reported moisture content was 93% for eggplant fruit (Website-2). The ash of a foodstuff in the inorganic residue remaining after the organic matter has been burnt away. The ash obtain is not necessarily of exactly the same compositions as the mineral matter present in the original food as there may be losses due to volatilization of some interaction between constituents (Pearson, 1970). Too high a temperature may cause the volatilization of certain elements, such as particularly potassium, sodium sulphur, chlorine and phosphorus and may also a cause the mineral matter to melt and fuse (Triebold and Aurand, 1963). Ash content of eggplant fruit was found to be in the range of 0.22-0.25 %. From these results, moisture and ash content of eggplant from prepared normal superphosphate treated plot (T_2) has slightly higher than other treated plots. Proteins are complex, nitrogenous organic compounds that essential to life process are necessary constituents of animal foods. The Kjeldahl method estimates the total nitrogen which is converted to total crude protein dependent on the proportion of the various nitrogenous compounds present in particular sample. The protein content of eggplant was found to be in the range of 0.85-1.08 % as shown in Table 9 .The protein content of eggplant fruit from prepared triple superphosphate treated plot (T_1) has slightly higher than that of other treated plots. All these values were in agreement with the reported nutritional value of 1 and 0.9% for eggplant fruit (Website-2). Soil testing is an important tool to measure the soil nutrient changes. Table 5 showed the physical parameters and chemical compositions in terms of N, P, K, Ca and Mg of farm soil media before transplanting (maize and eggplant). These soils were subjected to different treatments by using the prepared phosphate fertilizers (phosphoric acid, normal and triple superphosphate) and also the soil, without any fertilizer treatment, which was kept as a control. After harvesting of maize and eggplant, the soil analysis was carried out again. The data are presented in Table 11 for maize and eggplant.

Table 11. Analysis Data of the Farm Soil of Maize Plant and Eggplant after Harvesting

No	Item	Farm Soil of Maize Plant				Farm Soil of Eggplant			
		T_1	T_2	T_3	T_4	T_1	T_2	T_3	T_4
1	Texture – Sand (%)	17.03	17.05	17.00	16.37	16.35	16.53	16.5	16.35
	Silt (%)	34.71	34.76	34.75	34.63	34.79	34.75	34.74	34.66
	Clay (%)	45.01	45.00	45.02	44.97	45.02	45.03	45.0	44.98
	Total (%)	96.75	96.81	96.77	96.97	96.16	96.31	96.24	95.99
2	Moisture (%)	6.63	6.65	6.68	6.59	6.65	6.62	6.69	6.45
3	pH	6.7	6.6	6.5	6.5	6.7	6.8	6.5	6.5
4	Electrical Conductivity (mS/ cm)	0.171	0.17	0.173	0.103	0.173	0.171	0.174	0.104
5	Organic Carbon (%)	0.83	0.86	0.83	0.8	0.85	0.87	0.88	0.83
6	Humus (%)	3.71	3.68	3.65	3.31	3.68	3.24	2.13	3.26
7	Total N (%)	0.133	0.137	0.132	0.125	0.131	0.129	0.132	0.127
8	Available P (ppm)	34.19	26.52	23.42	19.87	17.02	16.71	16.91	15.2
9	Available K_2O (mg/ 100 g)	12.31	11.31	10.34	9.71	12.36	11.35	10.63	9.85
10	Exchangeable Ca^{++} (mmol/ 100 g)	11.34	11.23	9.92	9.16	11.21	11.05	9.68	9.12
11	Exchangeable Mg^{++} (mmol/ 100 g)	0.583	0.578	0.471	0.463	0.565	0.567	0.478	0.45

The soil texture was determined by how much sand, slit and clay are in the soil. The farm soil at all stages contained about 17% sand, 34% silt and 45% clay, so it was clay type.

Soil high in clay content will fix more phosphorus than those containing less clay. This type of soil texture has a greater water holding capacity but results less penetration of roots. Clay are the most complex and chemically active of inorganic soil particles. Clay particles are the negatively charged constituents of soils. These negatively charged clay colloids attract, hold and release positively charged secondary nutrients of plants such as K^+ , Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Na^+ , H^+ and NH_4^+ and some react with phosphorus. Regardless of clay type, fertilizer P is rapidly converted to less available forms. The texture of soil did not change much in the fertilizer treated plots. The added fertilizers only enhanced the soil fertility. According to Table 5, the pH values of soil at all stages were found to be in the range of 5.9-6.5. Since, there was no significant change in the pH of the soil used in the planting and harvesting stages, it can be considered that applied fertilizers did not affect the pH value of the soil. Increasing soil moisture to optimum levels makes P more available to plants. But excess moisture reduces O_2 , limiting root growth and slowing P uptake. The moisture content of control soil and treated soils were about the same. Only a slight decrease was observed after harvesting the plants. The humus content of the treated soil was about 4% before plantation and 3% after harvesting. Humus is a potential soil food for plant growth and yield. Organic carbon contents of control and treated soil before and after plantation were about 0.8%.

The content of micronutrients N, available P, K_2O , Ca and Mg of triple superphosphate treated soil (T_1) were higher than that of original control soil before plantation stage. After harvesting stage, total N, P, K_2O , Ca and Mg in the soil treated with prepared phosphate fertilizers, showed reduced amounts as compared to the treated soils before plantation. It can be ascertained that the plants have taken up N, P_2O_5 , K_2O , Ca and Mg on an enhance way.

Conclusion

This research work is concerned with the modification of local phosphate rock as a potential mineral fertilizer and preparation of phosphate fertilizers. The aim of this work undertaken is to explore in agriculture to improve soil fertility for agricultural productivity. The main types of phosphate rocks are apatite and phosphorite. In Myanmar, phosphate minerals as phosphorite occurred at the Thabeikyin area in Mandalay Division is the most prominent. It was found that phosphorite mineral sample from Thabeikyin Township, consists of 8.59 % of P_2O_5 , which is low and may not be used directly as fertilizers. Thus it is necessary to modify, so as to remove impurities and to upgrade the phosphate content, which is modified by wet screening and hydroseparation method. Based on computer matched patterns, Thabeikyin phosphate rock sample consists of two types of phosphate minerals, Vataselite $Al_4(PO_4)_3 \cdot 9H_2O$ and Brushite $CaHPO_4 \cdot (H_2O)_2$. The presence of major elements phosphorus, calcium, iron, potassium, chlorine and titanium in raw phosphate rock and upgraded phosphate minerals are identified by ED-XRF spectra and confirmed the higher amount of phosphorus content in upgraded sample. It was found that the raw mineral phosphate rock sample consists of 8.59 % P_2O_5 , 104.5 ppm Ca, 5.64 ppm Mg, 51.89 ppm K, 98.81 ppm Fe and 10.9 ppm Zn. The upgraded phosphate powder sample consists of 14.56 % P_2O_5 , 118.2 ppm Ca, 4.31 ppm Mg, 76.12 ppm Fe, 51.72 ppm K and 7.43 ppm Zn. Phosphate fertilizers (phosphoric acid, normal and triple superphosphate) were prepared from upgraded phosphate powder sample. In the physicochemical analysis data of the prepared phosphoric acid was found to be contained 8.74 % of P_2O_5 . The content of primary and secondary nutrients of superphosphates were 15.42 % of P_2O_5 , 8.65 % of Ca, 11.78 % of S and 7.3 % of K_2O in normal superphosphate and 18.94 % P_2O_5 , 8.32 % of Ca and 2.5 % of S in triple superphosphate. The field trial at the farm near Maubin University was conducted to study the effect of prepared phosphoric acid, normal

and triple superphosphate fertilizers on the plant growth and quality of cultivated plants. The comparison study on the performance of prepared phosphate fertilizers in the cultivation of maize and eggplant on neutral clay soils was done. Based on the plant growth (in terms of plant height), yield (kg/ha) and quality (size, weight, length, diameter, nutritional value, etc.) of the cultivated plants, it is ascertained that phosphate fertilizers prepared from the local phosphate rock are effective inorganic fertilizers which can enhance the agricultural productivity and sustain the soil fertility.

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Online Materials

1. <http://minerals.usgs.gov/minerals>
2. <http://www.eatingwell.com/articles-recipes/diabetic-exchanges/htt>